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STUDY OF THE TRIPLE SYSTEM AND ITS TRIANGULATION $Cs_2MoO_4 - MoV_2O_8 - MoO_3$ **Hasanaliev A.,***Doctor of Chemical Sciences, Professor of the Department of Chemistry of Dagestan State Pedagogical University named after Rasul Gamzatov***Israilov M.,***Candidate of Chemical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Chemistry of Chechen State Pedagogical University***Gasanalieva P.***Candidate of Chemical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Chemistry of Dagestan State Pedagogical University named after Rasul Gamzatov**Dagestan State Pedagogical University named after Rasul Gamzatov
Chechen State Pedagogical University**Research Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry, DSPU*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12580533>**Abstract**

The main task of physicochemical analysis is the study of multicomponent systems. Knowledge of phase levels and their regularities in multicomponent systems is necessary for the development of optimal conditions for the search for compositions with given conditions. $Cs_2MoO_4 - MoV_2O_8 - MoO_3$ Based on the results of experimental studies, the first promising areas of the phase diagram for the synthesis of vanadium-molybdenum bronzes of cesium were obtained. Compositions obtained on the basis of the system are promising in the development of new materials, in particular: anti-corrosion coatings, ion-electronic conductors with high activity.

Theoretically, according to the results of the data obtained, it has been proved that the synthesis of new materials from complex oxide phases by crystallization from the melt by solid-phase synthesis can be used to break down a three-component oxide system. $Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3$.

Keywords: compound, congruent, incongruent, diagram, phase complex, projection, liquidus, model, peritectics, segment, complex, system, prognosis, polytherm, stable complex, solid solutions, subsystem, bronzes, crystallization, quasobinary.

Using a set of methods of physical and chemical analysis, in particular, differential polythermal (DTA) [1], visual polythermal VPD [2] using the projection thermographic method (PTGM) [3] and platinum crucibles, Pt-Pt/Rh thermocouples served as a temperature meter. To record DTA curves, a device based on an electronic automatic potentiometer KSP-4 with an F-116 voltage amplifier was used. The calibration of the facility was carried out according to the temperatures of phase transitions of individual salts and their eutectic mixtures [4]. On the installation of a synchronous thermal analyzer, STA 409 PC (Luxx) from Netzsch, a derivatographic analysis was performed, designed for simultaneous temperature measurement, as well as registration of changes in the weight of weights in a wide temperature range (25-1500 C). Control over the measurement progress was carried out by built-in processors connected to a personal computer.

According to the literature [6-8], 14 new phases (13 polyoxosols and 1 bronze) are formed in the double systems of the oxide system under study, which cut the concentration triangle. Among them, 9 compounds are congruent and 5 are incongruent in nature. In this system, 14 HTCs are implemented, including 10 eutectic and 4 peritectic types.

Using the results of the study, we have constructed a topological image of the phase diagram of this system (Fig. 1). Only congruent-melting compounds are included here, they are just needed for triangulation.

Results and discussion. The most interesting, in our opinion, variants of triangulation are presented in Fig. 1. Here we have identified 9 triangulating sections. They divide it into 10 subsystems, which are quasi-three-component. Therefore, triple systems can be studied independently. To perform experimental work in the synthesis of individual compounds (D1 – D9) and thermal analysis of systems, modern methods of thermal analysis, in particular, the polythermal method, were also used. Modern methods of thermal analysis, in particular, visual-polythermic, differential-thermal, synchronous-thermal (STA) analysis by Netzsch [9-12]. Of these options, we have chosen (Fig. 1). Based on the results, 4 main subsystems are identified, which combine the rest: **I-II** - $CsVO_3 - MoV_2O_8 - V_2O_5$; **III** - $CsVO_3 - Cs_2MoO_4 - MoV_2O_8$; **IV-VI** - $CsVO_3 - Cs_2MoO_4 - Cs_2O$; **VII-X** - $Cs_2MoO_4 - MoV_2O_8 - MoO_3$.

Рис. 1

Рис. 2

Рис. 3

Рис. 4

Рис. 5

For one compound ratio and brand of h.p. solid-phase synthesis, in which molecules are covalently bonded on a solid carrier and synthesized step by step in a single reaction vessel using silicate chemistry of protection groups. [13] $M_0V_2O_8Cs_2M_0O_4CsVO_3$

Topological analysis and review of the facet elements of the ternary oxide system with its subsequent triangulation revealed that it implements (Fig. 1) 21 double and two-component and 10 ternary and three-component systems.

In the system chosen by us (Fig. 1), it $Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3$ includes 11 binary (1-11), 10 quasi-two-component (12-21), 3 ternary (IV-VI), 7 quasi-three-component (I-VI, VIII-X) systems, of which 5 quasi-binary (5,12,13,20,21) of the quasibar (1,VI,X) are oxide-salt systems, the rest are included in the complex oxide phases, which are polyvanates (D5 – D8) and polyvanadate molybdenum (D9). A three-component oxide system was split. $Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3$

The regularities of topology and phase formation in them were revealed, and the scientific basis of chemical technology was created on their basis. As part of the general study of multicomponent systems using the developed methods, a topological analysis of the system itself was carried out. [14-15]

The chosen methodological approach to the secondary unification of subsystems on the principle of minimizing a laborious experiment and achieving maximum information on the processes of phase formation in the system made it possible to solve the problems.

Another variant of triangulation (Fig. 5) is the maximum set of salt subsystems (1-4, 6-11; VI, III, V-IX), taking into account the facing oxide systems, provides forecasting and planning of the experiment.

The purpose of this work is to predict, simulate and experimentally confirm phase formation in the system of $Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3$ its stable and metastable processes. We have revealed the mechanisms, nature, conditions of formation and decay, qualitative and quantitative composition of new phases as much as possible. Triangulation (Fig. 1) The preliminary forecast was made by us on the basis of the analysis of diagrams of the state of triangulating sections (Fig. 3) and (Fig. 2) and (Fig. 2) compositions, which were confirmed by thermal analysis with subsequent confirmation by thermogravimetric and X-ray phase analysis. [15-16] Partitioning of the first 2 of them has complete phase diagrams, 7 new phases are formed in them, with the incongruent nature of melting by persthetic reactions. (Transformation – persthetic process – transformation occurs at a constant temperature) This indicates their metastability. A stable picture is observed in the D9 section $D_5(Cs_2M_0O_4 - V_2O_5)D_2(CsVCO_3)D_5(M_0V_2O_8) - Cs_2OCs_2O$, since eutectic processes predominate.

Conclusion.

On the basis of theoretical analysis and experimental data, the division of a three-component oxide system was carried out. The $Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3$ regularities of topology and phase formation in them were revealed, the system was triangulated for the first

time within the framework of the general algorithm for studying multicomponent systems using the results. Ten triangulation sections were identified, which are divided into 10 subsystems. Various oxide-salt compositions system-based promising in the development of new materials. In particular, anti-corrosion coatings, ion-electronic conductors, with high activity catalysts, reference electrodes for potentiometric redox and acid-base titrations, electro-optical materials. It should be noted in the synthesis of vanadium-molybdenum and mixed bronzes and polyvanadates-molybdates of cesium, which will find their application. $Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3$

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